

Tool 7

Impact statement

Welcome to the Citizen Science Starter Kit.

This template is part of Module 4 “Getting started with citizen science” (phase 1 – Prepare), which helps you to reflect on the potential impact of your project.

Please download this template to your own folder and fill it in on your local computer. If you have any further questions about this template, please contact citizenscience@vub.be.

Use the pointers below to reflect on, and write down, an impact statement.

Step 1. Write an answer to the following question in the box below: If in 2030 you wake up and your research has made a change in society, what do you see in the world around you that shows you this change? Feel free to talk this over with a colleague or other involved stakeholder.

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Step 2. Write down 5 words that are essential in this story and should/might be added in the statement.

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Step 3. Phrase your impact statement. Don’t worry, you can always come back to revisit it if you feel like something is still missing. Consider this statement as a guide, not only to yourself but also to convey to other stakeholders. Here are some additional guidelines for writing your statement.

An impact statement:

- Briefly summarizes, in lay terms, the difference your research efforts aim to make.
- Answers the questions... "So what?" and "Who cares?"
- States who will be affected by the work done, and how.

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